

SUPPLEMENTAL DATA

Stability of C₃ and C₄ Grass Patches in Woody Encroached Rangeland after Fire and Simulated Grazing

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Table S1. Fire treatments in the study, and fire steps within each treatment. All fires were conducted in the 1990's (e.g., w91 = winter 1991).

Treatment Short Name	Treatment Long Name	Steps in Each Fire Treatment	Time Burned
No Fire	No Fire	None	None
3WF	Repeated winter fires	w91+w93+w95	Late January to early March
3AF	Alternate-season fires	w91+s92+w94	Winter - Late January to early March; Summer - early September
3AFC	Alternate-season fires compressed sequence	w93+s93+w96	Winter - Late January to early March; Summer - early September
2SF	Repeated summer fires	s92+s94	Early September
2SFC	Repeated summer fires compressed sequence	s93+s94	August; Early September

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16 Table S2. Pre-burn weather and herbaceous fine fuel, and peak fire temperature and fire intensity of each fire step in each fire treatment.
 17 Except for the two bottom rows, all values are means (\pm s.e.) of 3 plots (36 total prescribed fires and 1 wildfire). The last two rows are
 18 means of the replicates of all winter or summer fire steps (\pm s.e.). The s93 fire step in the 2FX treatment was due to an August 24, 1993
 19 wildfire; fire temperature and intensity were not recorded.

Treatments	Fire Step	Air Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	Relative Humidity (%)	Wind Speed (m/s)	Fine Fuel (g/m^2)	Peak Fire Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	Fireline Intensity (kW/m)
3WF	w91	14.4 \pm 2.6	33.0 \pm 8.9	4.5 \pm 1.5	249 \pm 43	590 \pm 16	183 \pm 30
	w93	20.9 \pm 0.8	29.3 \pm 1.8	5.0 \pm 1.3	266 \pm 11	627 \pm 39	2518 \pm 472
	w95	25.4 \pm 2.1	26.3 \pm 2.9	4.2 \pm 1.6	263 \pm 48	469 \pm 40	770 \pm 154
3AF	w91	23.8 \pm 1.5	25.3 \pm 4.3	6.6 \pm 1.0	269 \pm 19	--nd--	543 \pm 356
	s92	33.1 \pm 0.7	41.3 \pm 3.0	4.6 \pm 0.8	390 \pm 18	627 \pm 37	7796 \pm 960
	w94	24.2 \pm 0.2	32.0 \pm 2.1	2.5 \pm 0.1	143 \pm 18	441 \pm 58	2186 \pm 1477
3AFC	w93	16.8 \pm 2.4	29.7 \pm 6.8	4.3 \pm 0.5	271 \pm 11	570 \pm 13	2247 \pm 1091
	s93	35.7 \pm 1.8	32.3 \pm 1.2	3.4 \pm 0.3	207 \pm 15	656 \pm 42	1259 \pm 438
	w96	18.5 \pm 1.2	28.7 \pm 2.9	2.6 \pm 0.6	473 \pm 36	--nd--	3580 \pm 356
2SF	s92	33.5 \pm 1.0	27.0 \pm 3.8	2.1 \pm 0.4	278 \pm 54	632 \pm 29	3827 \pm 369
	s94	32.2 \pm 1.1	45.3 \pm 3.3	3.2 \pm 0.4	267 \pm 13	649 \pm 17	2690 \pm 358
2SFC	s93	35.0	25.0	5.6	254 \pm 12	--nd--	--nd--
	s94	32.6 \pm 0.4	46.7 \pm 0.3	4.4 \pm 0.3	171 \pm 10	571 \pm 18	5329 \pm 712
Mean Winter		20.6 \pm 1.0	29.2 \pm 1.6	4.2 \pm 0.5	276 \pm 22	536 \pm 51	1718 \pm 348
Mean Summer		33.7 \pm 0.5	36.3 \pm 2.2	3.9 \pm 0.3	261 \pm 21	627 \pm 14	4180 \pm 644

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Table S3. *Prosopis* root-kill, top-kill and stand foliage reduction in response to each step of each

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fire treatment. All values are means \pm standard error (n=3). Means with similar letters within

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each column are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$).

Fire Treatment	Step in Each Fire Treatment	Root-kill ¹	Complete	Stand Foliage
		(%)	Top-kill (%)	Reduction (%)
3WF	w91	2.2 \pm 1.7 ab	8.2 \pm 5.6 e	42.8 \pm 5.3 d
	w93	0.0 \pm 0.0 b	57.8 \pm 2.2 c	86.0 \pm 3.7 c
	w95	1.4 \pm 0.9 ab	63.2 \pm 3.5 bc	87.5 \pm 2.8 bc
3AF	w91	0.0 \pm 0.0 b	30.3 \pm 10.1 d	54.3 \pm 9.6 d
	s92	0.7 \pm 0.7 ab	81.6 \pm 2.6 ab	98.0 \pm 0.7 ab
	w94	1.4 \pm 0.9 ab	85.8 \pm 6.4 a	97.4 \pm 1.6 abc
3AFC	w93	0.0 \pm 0.0 b	61.5 \pm 20.8 bc	90.1 \pm 7.6 abc
	s93	2.4 \pm 1.2 ab	94.8 \pm 0.6 a	99.3 \pm 0.7 a
	w96	2.8 \pm 1.6 ab	93.1 \pm 0.8 a	98.3 \pm 1.5 ab
2SF	s92	0.4 \pm 0.4 b	95.3 \pm 2.9 a	98.9 \pm 0.8 ab
	s94	1.7 \pm 1.2 ab	89.2 \pm 3.9 a	98.5 \pm 1.1 ab
2SFC	s93	4.3 \pm 2.9 a	93.6 \pm 1.9 a	99.4 \pm 0.4 a
	s94	2.1 \pm 1.0 ab	96.9 \pm 1.8 a	99.9 \pm 0.0 a

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^{1/} Root-kill of 4.3% after the S93 wildfire was likely an overestimate as evaluation after the second fire in 1994 found root-kill to be only 2.1%.

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Table S4. Proc Mixed 3-way analysis for initially *Buchloe* and *Nassella* patches from fall 1996 to spring 1997. Bold values are $P \leq 0.05$. C4M = C₄ mid-grasses, C3A = C₃ annual grasses.

Effect	df	<i>Buchloe</i>	<i>Nassella</i>	C4M	C3A	Forb	Litter	Bare
<i>Buchloe</i> Patches								
Clip	1	<.0001	0.0062	0.0052	0.0269	0.4959	<.0001	0.0292
Fire	5	<.0001	0.0026	0.1418	0.0090	0.0516	<.0001	0.2626
Year	1	0.8964	0.0040	0.0417	<.0001	<.0001	<.0001	0.1044
Clip*Fire	5	0.1246	0.5297	0.7345	0.4461	0.3672	0.0414	0.4917
Clip*Year	1	<.0106	0.6395	0.3054	0.0269	0.2514	<.0001	0.1599
Fire*Year	5	0.4273	0.7967	0.9346	0.0090	0.1680	0.0121	0.6075
Clip*Fire*Year	5	0.4931	0.9415	0.8741	0.4461	0.3468	0.1081	0.7077
<i>Nassella</i> Patches								
Clip	1	<.0001	0.0003	0.6581	0.1377	0.2007	<.0001	<.0001
Fire	5	0.0020	0.0014	0.0152	0.0034	0.0346	<.0001	0.0003
Year	1	0.4441	<.0001	0.8115	<.0001	0.4671	<.0001	0.0214
Clip*Fire	5	0.9679	0.2598	0.5174	0.1708	0.4298	0.0029	0.0149
Clip*Year	1	0.8012	0.0032	0.3472	0.1377	0.0295	0.0341	0.8192
Fire*Year	5	0.9998	0.9596	0.9531	0.0034	0.1651	0.0002	0.1291
Clip*Fire*Year	5	0.9880	0.8313	0.9881	0.1708	0.5489	0.2878	0.8903

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Figure S1. C₃ annual grass (C3A) and forb cover in *Buchloe* patches in response to fire treatments No Fire, 3WF and 3AF in winter ('f') or summer ('F') and clipping (c). Right panels show the frequent clipping treatments of Phase 1 (1992-1998). Right and left panels show the Phase 2 clipping treatment in 1999. Treatment code is in Table S1.

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3 Figure S2. C₃ annual grass (C3A) and forb cover in *Buchloe* patches in response to fire
 4 treatments 3AFC, 2SF and 2SFC in winter ('f') or summer ('F') and clipping (c). Right panels
 5 show the frequent clipping treatments of Phase 1 (1992-1998). Right and left panels show the
 6 Phase 2 clipping treatment in 1999. Treatment code is in Table S1.

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3 Figure S3. C₃ annual grass (C3A) and forb cover in *Nassella* patches in response to fire
 4 treatments No Fire, 3WF and 3AF in winter ('f') or summer ('F') and clipping (c). Right panels
 5 show the frequent clipping treatments of Phase 1 (1992-1998). Right and left panels show the
 6 Phase 2 clipping treatment in 1999. Treatment code is in Table S1.

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3 Figure S4. C₃ annual grass (C3A) and forb cover in *Nassella* patches in response to fire
 4 treatments 3AFC, 2SF and 2SFC in winter ('f') or summer ('F') and clipping (c). Right panels
 5 show the frequent clipping treatments of Phase 1 (1992-1998). Right and left panels show the
 6 Phase 2 clipping treatment in 1999. Treatment code is in Table S1.

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3 Figure S5. Litter and bare ground cover in *Buchloe* patches in response to fire treatments No
 4 Fire, 3WF and 3AF in winter ('f') or summer ('F') and clipping (c). Right panels show the
 5 frequent clipping treatments of Phase 1 (1992-1998). Right and left panels show the Phase 2
 6 clipping treatment in 1999. Treatment code is in Table S1.

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3 Figure S6. Litter and bare ground cover in *Buchloe* patches in response to fire treatments 3AFC,
 4 2SF and 2SFC in winter ('f') or summer ('F') and clipping (c). Right panels show the frequent
 5 clipping treatments of Phase 1 (1992-1998). Right and left panels show the Phase 2 clipping
 6 treatment in 1999. Treatment code is in Table S1.

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3 Figure S7. Litter and bare ground cover in *Nassella* patches in response to fire treatments No
 4 Fire, 3WF and 3AF in winter ('f') or summer ('F') and clipping (c). Right panels show the
 5 frequent clipping treatments of Phase 1 (1992-1998). Right and left panels show the Phase 2
 6 clipping treatment in 1999. Treatment code is in Table S1.

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3 Figure S8. Litter and bare ground cover in *Nassella* patches in response to fire treatments 3AFC,
4 2SF and 2SFC in winter ('f') or summer ('F') and clipping (c). Right panels show the frequent
5 clipping treatments of Phase 1 (1992-1998). Right and left panels show the Phase 2 clipping
6 treatment in 1999. Treatment code is in Table S1.

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